

“UMUMIY O’RTA TA’LIM MAKTABLARINING 7-SINF
O’QUVCHILARIGA AQLLI UY MODELINI YASASHNI O’RGATISH
METODIKASI”

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Annotatsiya: Maxalliy xom-ashyolardan umumta’lim maktablarida texnologiya fanini o‘qitish jarayonida o‘quvchilarda 7-sinfda aqlli uy modelini yasashni o‘rgatish metodikasini o‘qitishda kreativ yondashuvga oid ma’lumotlarni tadqiq qilamiz va aqlli uy modelini taklif qilamiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: Aqlli uy, texnologiya, xom-ashyo, Qurilish materiallari, foneks, yog‘och, bolt, gayka, mix, shrup, konselyar pichog‘i, o‘lchov metri, sirkul, sun‘iy to‘shama, boshqaruv pulti, montaj, favora, nasos, uycha.

Аннотация: В рамках обучения технологиям в средних школах мы изучим информацию о творческом подходе к обучению учащихся 7-го класса созданию модели «умного дома» с использованием местных сырьевых материалов и предложим модель «умного дома».

Ключевые слова: Умный дом, технологии, сырье, строительные материалы, телефон, дерево, болт, гайка, гвоздь, шуруп, ножницы, рулетка, компас, искусственная трава, панель управления, монтаж, вентилятор, насос, корпус.

Annotation: We will study information on a creative approach to teaching students how to build a smart home model in 7th grade using local raw materials in the process of teaching technology in secondary schools and propose a smart home model.

Key words: Smart home, technology, raw materials, construction materials, phonex, wood, bolt, nut, nail, screw, scissors, tape measure, compass, artificial grass, control panel, installation, fan, pump, housing.

Natijalar:

Aqlli uy texnologiyalari zamonaviy uy hayotini inqilob qilib, uni qulay, xavfsiz va samarali qiladi. Aqlli qurilmalar nafaqat uy yumushlarini osonlashtiradi, balki energiya sarfini kamaytirish va xavfsizlikni ta’minlashga ham yordam beradi. Kelajakda IoT texnologiyalari va aqlli uy qurilmalarining kengayishi bilan bizning uylarimiz nafaqat aqlli, balki butunlay ekologik toza va tejamkor bo‘lishi kutilmoqda. Aqlli uylar yordamida texnologiya hayotimizning ajralmas qismiga

aylanishi mumkin va odamlar o'z uylarida yashashdan ko'proq zavqlanishadi. Yuqoridagilarni inobatga olib biz maxalliy xom-ashyolardan umumta'lim maktablarida texnologiya fanini o'qitish jarayonida o'quvchilarda 7-sinfda aqlli uy modelini yasashni o'rgatish metodikasini o'qitishda kreativ yondashuvga oid ma'lumotlarni tadqiq qilamiz. Quyida aqlli uy modelini taklif qilamiz.

Texnologi xarita

T/r	Ish ketma-ketligi	Ish eskizi yoki texnik rasmi	jihoz va moslamalar
1	Qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup va sun'iy to'shama olinadi	<p style="text-align: center; color: red;">foneks</p> <p style="text-align: center; color: red;">yog'och mahsuloti</p> <p style="text-align: center; color: red;">shruplar</p>	foneks,yog'och, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup , konselyar pichog'i,o'lchov metri,sirkul va sun'iy to'shama
2	foneks kerakli o'lchamlarda kesib olinadi va aqlli uy karkasiga arduino mahkamlanadi		qurilish materiallaridan foneks,yog'och, mix,shrup,konselyar pichog'i,o'lchov metri,sirkul,arduino

<p>elektr montaj ishlari bajariladi</p>		<p>elementlar ketma-ketlikda montaj qilib chiqiladi</p>
<p>boshqaruv pulti montaj qilinadi</p>		<p>boshqaruv pulti</p>
<p>elektrdvigatellar uy maketga mahkamlanadi</p>		<p>elektrdvigatel, similar, yelim</p>
<p>hamma elementlar karkasga mahkamlanadi</p>		<p>Qurilish materiallari, foneks,yog'och, bolt,gayka,mix,shrup , konselyar pichog'i,o'lchov metri,sirkul, sun'iy to'shama, boshqaruv pulti,montaj, favora,nasos,uycha.</p>

3

tayyor elektrostend
elektr manbaga
ulanib boshqaruv
pulti yordamida
ishga tushiriladi

boshqaruv pulti

tayyor elektrostend

Muhokama:

Karkasga arduino kompleksi, favora, nasos, uycha, sun'iy gilamcha va uyni mahkamlab chiqib stendni montaj qismini nihoyalaymiz (1-rasm).

1-rasm

Xulosa:

2-rasm

Arduino, himoya korpusi va simlar bilan ulanib elektrstendni boshqaruv pultiga ulashga tayyorlaymiz (2-rasm, 3-rasm).

3-rasm

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